

LOGIC CALC: A DESIGN TOOL FOR DIGITAL SYSTEMS

Captain Glenn D. Rosenberger

Department of Electrical Engineering
United States Air Force Academy, Colorado

ABSTRACT

Logic Calc, a spreadsheet program, was developed to be used as a tool for the design of digital systems. Use of Logic Calc presents a simple, interactive, highly visible, self-documenting method of designing digital systems at various levels of abstraction. Logic Calc allows the designer several capabilities not offered by financial spreadsheets, including an ability to specify the size in bits of each spreadsheet cell. This allows spreadsheet cells to closely represent registers, databuses, and other digital hardware of various sizes. Another specialized feature of Logic Calc is an ability to simulate registers and other key components of a digital system in a single spreadsheet cell. This paper presents the use of Logic Calc as a digital design tool.

INTRODUCTION

At the initial stages of design of a digital system, stages in which many changes are usually made, an ideal design tool would be interactive, flexible, highly visible, and self-documenting. Financial spreadsheet programs have these characteristics, and have been proven to have the capability to support the design and simulation of digital systems (1, 4, 5, 7). Each cell within a spreadsheet can represent fundamental components within a digital system (Figure 1). The cell's formula is used to describe the operation of the component. The spreadsheet offers an interactive means of editing cells through use of cursor positioning and menu selection techniques. The cell's value, displayed on the screen, depicts the output state of the component in a highly visible manner. Because a spreadsheet cell can represent computer "black boxes" at various levels of abstraction, a high degree of flexibility is offered with such a design tool.

Financial spreadsheets are widely available, but they have several drawbacks when used as digital design tools. These drawbacks stem from the design of such spreadsheets as financial tools rather than engineering tools. The primary shortcomings of financial spreadsheet programs when used for digital system design are:

1. A maximum value for fixed-point integers. Financial spreadsheets typically do not allow fixed-point integers to be greater than preset limits. If integers become too large in a financial spreadsheet, they are automatically converted to floating point numbers. In a digital system, however, many components, such as microstore, hold binary integer values in excess of financial spreadsheet's maximum integer value. When used to represent such digital components, floating-point numbers are not acceptable because they do not represent a true bit image of device contents.

2. Fixed size integers. Registers and buses have various bit lengths. A flag register may consist of only a single bit, whereas microstore may consist of hundreds of bits. In simulation of digital systems, financial spreadsheets lack an ability to correctly represent hardware of various sizes because all cells have the same bit length in a financial spreadsheet.

Figure 1. Spreadsheet Cell A8 Functioning as a Digital Selector

3. Lack of Boolean operations. Boolean logic is the heart of all digital systems. Typically, Boolean operations in a financial spreadsheet can only be accomplished with complicated if-then constructs. This method of simulating Boolean operations is cumbersome and error-prone.

4. Lack of binary and hexadecimal display. Interpreting decimal values in a binary system is also cumbersome and can lead to errors by the user.

5. Inability to represent some key digital components in a single cell. To represent some digital units, a financial spreadsheet requires several cells, cluttering the display. (6, 7)

6. Slow and cumbersome programmatic operation of the spreadsheet. Lotus 1-2-3, a popular spreadsheet, offers "macros" to drive a spreadsheet, but these macros have an unusual syntax and are therefore difficult to write. Also, they are interpreted rather than compiled; therefore, their execution speed is slow.

7. No modification capabilities. The uncompiled, high-level language source code is unavailable for most financial spreadsheets, making it difficult to modify the spreadsheet for specific applications.

Logic Calc, a public-domain spreadsheet program created by the author, eliminates these shortcomings. It offers an interactive, highly-visible design environment for digital systems. Logic Calc is implemented in Common Lisp on a Texas Instruments Explorer workstation.

LOGIC CALC DATA STRUCTURE

Basically, a spreadsheet is a two-dimensional array of a data object called a "cell." An individual, unique cell can be referenced through use of the array indexes, typically called "rows" and "columns." Each cell has specific properties including a type, value, display characteristics, and possibly a formula used to derive its value from its relationships with data and other cells within the spreadsheet. The power in a spreadsheet is two-fold:

1. It has an ability to change and recalculate the values of every cell whenever changes are made to the data or the cell formulas.

2. It provides an interactive environment for editing of data and cell formulas.

These two features allow rapid "what if?" analysis of a wide variety of problems. The array format of a spreadsheet provides both a structure for numeric data for easy recalculation and a format for displaying the data and calculations (5).

There are four types of spreadsheet cells in Logic Calc: a null cell, a constant cell, a string cell, and a formula cell. Each Logic Calc spreadsheet cell contains six properties. Two of these properties are not usually found in traditional spreadsheet cells: the bits property

and the changed-value property. The following is a list of the Logic Calc cell properties:

1. Value. This property of the spreadsheet can be either an integer of any size, an ASCII string, or nil, depending upon the type of cell. This value is displayed on the spreadsheet window in a format specified by the output-display property. If the cell is not a formula type, this value is constant. If the cell is a formula, this value is the result of a calculation of the cell formula.

2. Formula. Although all cells contain this property, only formula cells make use of it. This property is a Lisp form that is evaluated upon each spreadsheet recalculation to determine the cell's value. This Lisp form utilizes a prefix notation which is easy to read and evaluate. For example, the infix formula of $(3+5)/2$ would be written in prefix form as $(/ (+ 3 5) 2)$.

3. Recalculation flag. This flag is used to ensure that each cell is evaluated only once during spreadsheet recalculation. Logic Calc recalculation methods and circular references are discussed later in this paper.

4. Bits. This property, unique to Logic Calc, stems from the design goal of making Logic Calc a design tool for digital systems. The bits property, set by the user or defaulted to 32, allows a cell to exactly represent the number of bits in a register, databus, or other component. Cells which have integer values are restricted to a value that can be specified with the prescribed number of bits given by the cell's bit property. Because internal values are adjusted by this property, negative values show a true two's complement form of leading 1's in the left-most bit positions and are displayed without a minus sign. For example, subtracting decimal four from decimal three with a cell formula of $(- 3 4)$ will yield a value of FFFFFFFF hexadecimal, which is negative one decimal. Overflow of a cell is also possible due to this property. For example, a three-bit cell with a formula of $(+ 2 7)$ will yield a result of 1. Due to Lisp's ability to accommodate integers of any size, cells of any bit size can be accommodated by Logic Calc (6).

5. Output display. This property, set by the user during spreadsheet editing, determines whether a numeric cell is displayed in binary or hexadecimal.

6. Changed value flag. During editing or spreadsheet recalculation, this flag is set whenever a cell changes its value. The external display can be rapidly updated by reprinting only those cells whose value has changed since the last display update.

LOGIC CALC FORMULA CELLS

Formula cells form the heart of the spreadsheet - without them, a spreadsheet would be merely a cute data storage and display device. Because Logic Calc cell formulas are both written and stored as a Lisp form, a user needs to learn

only one syntax to utilize Logic Calc directly or to interface to Logic Calc from other programs. When used to design digital systems, the Lisp syntax and semantics prove far more powerful than that used by financial spreadsheets due to Lisp's straight-forward, unambiguous syntax, its ease of editing, and its ability to perform operations not conveniently offered by financial spreadsheets - specifically, Boolean operations. Also, because Logic Calc cell formulas are written in the same language that Logic Calc is written in, the user will find it easy to make modifications to the Logic Calc source code once he learns how to write simple cell formulas. Thus, he can easily tailor Logic Calc to his own needs.

Cell formulas are written to reference the values of other cells within the spreadsheet. These formulas provide the necessary relationships between spreadsheet cells for the cells to represent discrete digital components. Traditional spreadsheet relationships can be expressed, such as (+ (Cell F15) (Cell F16)) to return the sum of cells F15 and F16. Logic Calc goes a step further, however by providing cell formulas for indirection and lookup. Logic Calc also provides special purpose formulas that enable spreadsheet cells to function as specific digital components. One such formula is the "Dual-Rank-Register" formula that allows a single cell to represent a dual rank register. Furthermore, Logic Calc also allows the user to define his own cell formulas, thereby allowing the user to tailor Logic Calc to his own applications. This capability for user-defined functions also provides simulation to occur at various levels of abstraction: cell formulas can be written to describe simple or very complex digital components.

As a digital systems design tool, a key advantage of Logic Calc over financial spreadsheets is its ability to perform Boolean operations. Logic Calc cell formulas can utilize Lisp Boolean operators to perform logical operations at the cell, byte, or bit levels (2).

LOGIC CALC OPERATION

The user interface of Logic Calc consists of a team of three windows that share a common input buffer (Figure 2).

The largest window, the spreadsheet window, depicts the row and column indexes and the values of the cells that can fit within the window. The designer uses a mouse to select spreadsheet cells, columns or rows for viewing, editing, copying, moving, inserting or deleting.

The second window is the Interaction Window. This window is used to output information requested by the user, to display certain messages, and to input user responses to various program prompts. Essentially, anything that must be typed by the user to edit the spread sheet is generally input through this window.

The third window is the Logic Calc Main Menu. This menu allows the designer use of the mouse to initiate file operations, change the size of the spreadsheet, select the region of the spreadsheet to be viewed, recalculate the spreadsheet, or exit the spreadsheet to terminate editing operations.

In Logic Calc, a simulation of the design is initialized and driven by a Logic Calc driving program. This driving program simply controls the operation of the spreadsheet in a manner similar to the "macros" of Lotus 1-2-3. To write and execute a Logic Calc driving program, Logic Calc is exited normally. The driving program can then be written and executed from the ZMACS editor, the primary editor of the Texas Instruments Explorer. ZMACS offers extensive full-screen editing operations, file operations, and incremental compilation and interpretation capabilities (3).

The Logic Calc driving program can also represent digital components at several levels of abstraction. During the simulation, the driving program can function as a controlling processor, a microcontroller, or it can simply drive a clock. Several Lisp functions are provided by Logic Calc to aid in development of a driving program. These supplied functions can be invoked to recalculate the spreadsheet, load spreadsheet cells, test spreadsheet cells, and display intermediate results. As with the spreadsheet, the driving program can also utilize user-defined functions, allowing the designer to tailor Logic Calc to his own needs.

DIGITAL SYSTEM DESIGN AND SIMULATION WITH LOGIC CALC

Generally, the components in a digital system operate in parallel with a common clock synchronizing operations. A digital system also includes numerous logical units that form interconnections between the parallel components.

Figure 2. Logic Calc User Interface

These logical interconnections often form circular references: the output of Unit A is an input to Unit B, and the output of Unit B is the input to Unit A. Figure 3 depicts this concept of a digital system. A spreadsheet serves as a useful tool to represent a digital system because of its fundamental abilities to map parallel operations and their circular interconnections onto a single, serial processor.

In a digital system, the input into each register must be resolved before that register is clocked. This input is usually a Boolean combination of other registers, memory, and control signals. To represent a digital system, a spreadsheet must maintain the proper relationships between components. For example, if a Logic Calc spreadsheet was made to model the circuit in Figure 4, six cells would be needed to represent the components: one for each data bus, one for each register, and one for the combinational logic circuit. In this example digital system, the output of the combinational logic circuit must be resolved before clocking of Register A. Similarly, in Logic Calc, the equation for the cell representing the combinational logic circuit must be calculated before the equation for the cell representing Register A. Also, in the example digital system, the clocking of both registers occurs in parallel. In Logic Calc, the order of calculation for the cells representing the two registers is not important: independent parallel operating components can be calculated one at a time without regard to order.

In order to correctly map the parallel components with their interconnections onto a spreadsheet, two issues need to be resolved. First, the hierarchical dependency relationships between spreadsheet cells must be maintained to correctly simulate data flow. Second, spreadsheet cells involved in circular references must be recalculated only once. The solution used in Logic Calc to solve this problem utilizes a check of the parameters of each cell formula during spreadsheet recalculation. If a parameter of a cell formula is another formula cell, recalculation of the first cell is postponed until the second cell is recalculated. For example, during recalculation of cell F4, if a parameter of the cell F4's formula is found to be cell F16 and F16 is also a formula cell, the recalculation of cell F4 is postponed and the recalculation of cell F16 is begun. When cell F16 has been recalculated, the recalculation of cell F4 may be continued. This recalculation method maintains proper hierarchical relationships between cells and treats circular references properly, as shown in the next two paragraphs.

To implement this solution in Logic Calc, a global list of all formula cells is maintained. The recalculation flag in the cell property list is also used to prevent a formula cell from being recalculated more than once during a single spreadsheet recalculation. A spreadsheet recalculation is accomplished by first setting all formula cell's recalculation flag to nil. Next, each cell listed in "Formula-List" is sequentially recalculated. The first step during recalculation of a cell is to test the recalculation flag. If the flag is set to "true," the recalculation of that cell is not performed. If the flag is "nil",

the flag is set to "true" and the recalculation of that cell's formula is initiated. During recalculation of the cell's formula, if another formula cell is found to be a parameter of the formula, the current recalculation is postponed until recalculation of the cell used as a parameter is accomplished. It can be shown that this method of recalculation produces identical results regardless of the ordering of "Formula-List" (6).

Figure 3. Concept of a Digital System

Figure 4. Example Digital Circuit

Digital systems of appreciable size will have circular references. Logic Calc's method of recalculation generates only one recalculation of spreadsheet cells involved in a circular reference. The simplest example of a circular reference is a cell functioning as a counter. If cell A1 were to have the formula (+ 1 (Cell A1)), a circular reference is established because this cell refers to itself. The Logic Calc program will increment this cell by one for each spreadsheet recalculation. Logic Calc also handles more complex circular references, involving several cells, regardless of the ordering of the entries under "Formula-List."

A fundamental aspect of a digital system is that many components utilize a clock to load registers and synchronize operations. Logic Calc presents a simple way for simulating the clock in a digital system. Every recalculation of the spreadsheet can be made to simulate one of four states of a clock: the rising edge, the high level, the falling edge, and the low level. To accomplish this, one of the cells within the spreadsheet can be made to iterate between four values with each value describing one of the four states of the clock. Other cells, functioning as clocked digital components, can use conditional constructs in their cell formulas to test the value of the "clock" cell. This will enable the cells functioning as clocked digital components to act differently for each state of the simulated clock.

When testing a digital system on Logic Calc, clocking of the digital system can be initiated in two ways. The user can simply click the mouse on the "Calc" item from the Logic Calc Main Menu to initiate a single spreadsheet recalculation and change the state of the clock. Four clicks on the "Calc" item would be necessary to generate a full clock cycle. An alternative method would be to exit Logic Calc and execute a driving program that generates clock pulses. These two methods for clocking the digital system provide both an incremental design-and-test capability (through use of the Main Menu), and a method for large scale testing (use of the driving program).

RESULTS

Logic Calc's capabilities have been demonstrated by using it to design a simple microprocessor (6). This microprocessor was based upon the Motorola 6800 family of microprocessors. It contained two 32-bit general purpose registers, two 32-bit index registers, a 32-bit stack register, a simple ALU (add, subtract, increment, decrement), a microcontroller with a 22-bit wide microinstruction, a 156-bit microstore, and sufficient ROM and RAM to support testing of the design. Forty-eight macro instructions were written. Using Logic Calc, the design of this microprocessor required only thirty man-hours. Logic Calc's incremental design-and-test capabilities were used throughout the design process, so final testing was approached with a high degree of confidence. Final testing and verification of the design was also accomplished using Logic Calc. Several programs were loaded into the "memory" of the microprocessor, and a

Logic Calc automatic simulation was run to verify the performance of the microprocessor design. Although this design process was primarily academic in nature, it fully demonstrated Logic Calc's capabilities as a digital design tool.

CONCLUSION

Logic Calc is an effective tool for the design of digital systems. Logic Calc is most useful at relatively high levels of abstraction, where most traditional design tools lack an ability to simulate and test a design. At a high level of abstraction, Logic Calc can be used to design digital systems in an interactive, highly visible, self-documenting environment. The high-level digital system, designed and tested with Logic Calc, can be passed down to the next level of design with sufficient detail and documentation to ensure that no design errors are passed down.

Patterned after financial spreadsheets, Logic Calc retained many general purpose features of a financial spreadsheet. Future versions of Logic Calc will address further specialization of the spreadsheet for design of digital systems (6). Interested readers can contact the author at the Electrical Engineering Department, United States Air Force Academy, for further information and a copy of Logic Calc.

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